

A Review on Methotrexate Used in Rheumatoid Arthritis

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Abstract

Since the 1980s, methotrexate has been used to treat rheumatoid arthritis (RA), and it is still frequently used as the first medicine to treat RA. In this review, we look at a variety of theories to help us understand how methotrexate works to treat RA. Among them are the antagonistic effects of folate, adenosine signaling, the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), the reduction of adhesion molecules, the changing of cytokine profiles, and the suppression of polyamines. The methotrexate mechanism in RA is currently most commonly explained via adenosine signaling. As a result of methotrexate's ability to raise adenosine levels and the activation of an intracellular cascade by adenosine's interaction with extracellular receptors, which reduces inflammation overall. In addition to these theories, we also take into account some of the more recent genetic indicators of methotrexate efficacy and toxicity in RA as well as the mechanism of methotrexate in RA from the standpoint of its negative consequences. Finally, we briefly go over how methotrexate works in combination with TNF-inhibitors to treat RA. Ultimately, developing more effective treatments with fewer adverse effects may be possible if the pathway and mechanism leading to methotrexate efficacy in RA are clearly understood.

Keywords: Methotrexate, ophthalmology, therapy, toxicity

1. Introduction: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic, symmetrical, inflammatory autoimmune disease that initially affects small joints, progressing to larger joints, and eventually the skin, eyes, heart, kidneys, and lungs. Often, the bone and cartilage of joints are destroyed, and tendons and ligaments weaken [1]. All this damage to the joints causes deformities and bone erosion, usually very painful for a patient. Common symptoms of RA include morning stiffness of the affected joints for >30 min, fatigue, fever, weight loss, joints that are tender, swollen and warm, and rheumatoid nodules under the skin. The onset of this disease is usually from the age of 35 to 60 years, with remission and exacerbation. It can also afflict young children even before the age of 16 years, referred to as juvenile RA (JRA), which is similar to RA except that rheumatoid factor is not found [2–5]. In the West, the prevalence of RA is believed to be 1–2% [5, 6], and 1% worldwide [7]. Clinically, the diagnosis of RA can be differentiated from osteoarthritis (OA) as the affected areas in RA are the proximal interphalangeal (PIP) and metacarpophalangeal (MP) joints; OA typically affects the distal interphalangeal (DIP) joint (Fig. 1). OA is the most common type of arthritis and is caused by wear and tear rather than an autoimmune condition. It has no effects on the lungs, heart, or immune system. In addition, OA typically affects only one side of the body, as opposed to the symmetrical nature of RA. Another differentiating factor is that RA patients suffer from persistent morning stiffness for at least ≥ 1 h. Patients with OA may have morning stiffness, but

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this typically resolves or decreases within 20–30 min [8, 9]. The goals of treatment for RA are to reduce joint inflammation and pain, maximize joint function, and prevent joint destruction and deformity. Treatment regimens consist of combinations of pharmaceuticals, weightbearing exercise, educating patients about the disease, and rest. Treatments are generally customized to a patient's needs and depend on their overall health. This includes factors such as disease progression, the joints involved, age, overall health, occupation, compliance, and education about the disease [10]. This review briefly highlights the classic and current treatment options available to address the discomfort/complications of RA. An exhaustive review was recently published by Smolen et al. [11] Although there has been development of numerous new targeted therapies for rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in recent years, methotrexate has remained the “anchor drug” for most patients since the late 1980s [12]. MTX has also been widely applied in ophthalmic diseases, systemically and locally. Recently published articles pay more attention to new clinical applications, routes of administration, and newly discovered side effects, which are foci of this review. However, despite its long-term and widespread use for RA, the precise mechanism of this drug remains elusive. Methotrexate was originally designed as a folate pathway antagonist by inhibiting di-hydro-folate reductase (DHFR) when given at very high doses for leukemia (as high as 1 gram in a single dose), but it was found that at much lower doses (15–25 mg weekly) the drug was effective in RA patients [13]. The oncologic mechanism of action involves inhibition of purine synthesis and thus arrest in the S phase of the cell cycle eventually leading to apoptosis of cells [14]. The clinical effects of high dose methotrexate used in cancer including the adverse effects can be reversed with high doses of calcium or folic acid [15]. On the other hand, the efficacy of low-doses of methotrexate used in RA patients is unaffected by the administration of folic acid and it is in fact almost invariably part of the RA medication regimen to minimize the unwanted methotrexate side a way to formulate more potent therapies with fewer side effects [16]. This indicates that inhibition of purine metabolism is unlikely to be the major mechanism of methotrexate in RA and that another element must be accounting for efficacy of methotrexate in RA patients.

2. Clinical Applications in Ophthalmology: As one of the known corticosteroids-sparing agents, MTX has been widely used in the treatment of anterior, intermediate, posterior, or pan uveitis; scleritis; and ocular mucous membrane pemphigoid [17], as well as advanced proliferative diabetic retinopathy [18]. However, followed researches reveal that MTX works with a significant difference in effectiveness ratings by anatomic location of inflammation [19], with treatment success achieved most commonly in patients with anterior uveitis and scleritis [20]. In the treatment of noninfectious intraocular inflammation, oral and intravenous are the most common routes with a usual dose range of 7.5 mg to 25 mg weekly. The typical dose observed was 12.5 mg/week [20, 21], which is in the range of low-dose MTX. Median time to achieve the success of Hindawi Journal of Ophthalmology Volume 2020, Article ID 1537689, 11 pages, defined as control of inflammation with the ability to taper corticosteroids to 10 mg or less daily, ranges from 4.5 months to 9 months for MTX [22- 23]. Intravitreal MTX injection, with or without systemic chemotherapy and radiotherapy, has already been used to treat primary intraocular lymphoma patients [24, 27]. According to Larkin et al. [28],

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intravitreal MTX injection could achieve remission in a proportion of patients with primary intraocular lymphoma. What is particularly noteworthy is that although MTX has a slow rate of onset of effect, when it was used to treat intraocular lymphoma via intravitreal injection, it prolonged local remission of ocular disease even with an aggressively growing tumor [24]. Therefore, it has been taken as a relatively first-line choice for the treatment of recurrent intraocular lymphoma [25], although the treatment for primary intraocular lymphoma is lacking solid justification because of the limited retrospective and prospective case series [29]. Local treatment via intraocular injection provides a consistent therapeutic MTX concentration to reduce the systemic MTX associated side effects [27]. Therefore, intraocular MTX injection is worth trying, especially for unilateral ocular diseases.

3. New Approaches of Applications of MTX: MTX Used against Epithelial Downgrowth.

Previous studies have already demonstrated safety of intravitreal MTX [26]. It has been used to treat intraocular lymphoma and proliferative vitreoretinopathy because of its antiproliferative properties [30]. There is a novel use of intravitreal MTX for recurrent epithelial down growth which was not treated by surgical and medical methods. Lambert et al. [31] administered intravitreal MTX to patients with refractory proliferative membrane after cataract surgery, while membrane peel and endo-laser treatment failed. The injection of MTX was administered alone, based on previous protocols and the presumed half-life of drugs in vitreous cavity. After 12 injections totally, there was no membrane recurrence. This case suggests that intravitreal MTX plays a role in treatment against epithelial downgrowth.

3.2. MTX Used in Conventional therapy-Resistant Diseases.

Generally, the anti-vascular endothelial growth factor (anti-VEGF) therapy has dramatically improved the prognosis of neovascular age-related macular degeneration (nAMD). However, there are still some patients who remain refractory to anti-VEGF therapy, which is termed as treatment-resistant nAMD. As there is evidence that MTX has effects in interrupting the angiogenesis cascade at various levels [32], offered intravitreal MTX to patients who were refractive to standard anti-VEGF therapy [33]. Although it was an off-label use, the patients' visual acuity improved at follow-up visit, while ophthalmic imaging examinations showed significantly reduced cystoid macular edema. Dietary folate enters the cells through RFC1, as well as MTX. In low-dose MTX treatment, MTX inhibits enzymes of the folate pathway. Ultimately, MTX leads to an increase in intracellular adenosine level, which would cause anti-inflammatory effects. RFC-1 reduced folate carrier 1; ABC family- adenosine triphosphate-binding cassette (ABC) family; DHF- dihydrofolate; THF- tetrahydrofolate; GGH- c-glutamyl hydrolase; FPG- foylpolylglutamate synthase; MTX-PG- methotrexate polyglutamate; DHFR- dihydrofolate reductase; MTHFR- methylene tetrahydrofolate reductase; AICAR- aminoimidazole carboxamide ribonucleotide; ATIC-AICAR transformylase. Journal of Ophthalmology patients who are refractory to traditional anti-VEGF therapy might benefit from intravitreal injection of MTX. This approach is not alone [34] had 400 µg/0.1 ml of MTX intravitreal injection once monthly administrated to 20 adult Behcet's disease (BD) patients suffering from BD-associated ocular inflammation with posterior segment involvement. Their results prove that intravitreal MTX improves visual acuity, reduces posterior segment manifestations associated with Behcet's disease, and allows

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the reduction of corticosteroids and immunosuppressive drugs [34]. These results also supported Taylor and associates who conducted trials on 15 patients with unilateral uveitis and/or cystoid macular edema [35]. Their clinical trials suggest that intravitreal MTX may help patients with uveitis-associated posterior segment involvement to regain normal anatomical structure and then allowed the reduction of immunosuppressive therapy. The Pharmacogenetics of MTX With molecular sequencing and high-throughput technology, large numbers of genetic polymorphisms can now be detected accurately and rapidly [36]. Researchers pay more attention to pharmacogenetics, the study of genetic polymorphisms in drug-metabolizing enzymes and the translation of inherited differences to differences in drug effects [37]. The genes encoding transporting proteins and metabolizing enzymes for MTX are also known to harbor functionally significant SNPs. The SNPs may influence the efficacy of MTX and have been suggested as potential risk factors for enhanced MTX toxicity, even in low-dose regimens, based on previous researches [38]. The research of pharmacogenetics of MTX could be divided into genetic polymorphisms affecting MTX transport and SNPs that influence enzymes in the cellular pathway of MTX [37]. Once taken, MTX enters the cell through an active transport which is mediated by the reduced folate carrier 1 (RFC1). The loss of RFC1 gene expression might lead to effects of uptake and intracellular levels of MTX. A G80A SNP of RFC1 was proposed [31] making a decreasing [40] or increasing [41, 42] effect on intracellular level of MTX. Therefore, a significant association between RFC1 SNPs and MTX toxicity should be considered. Thereby, state that these SNPs strongly impact the overall MTX associated side effects by resulting in altered cellular MTX concentration, but with no influence on MTX efficacy [43]. However, some researchers argue that these SNPs have no definite effect [44]. Thus, it remains controversial whether SNPs of RFC1 affect the transport of MTX. Moreover, P-glycoprotein, a membrane transporter that has influences on the disposition and bioavailability of MTX [45], was studied. SNPs of ABCB1, including C3435T SNP and C1236T SNP, were believed to have effects on the expression of P-glycoprotein [46]. Gervasini et al. speculate the C1236T SNP of ABCB1 affects the administered doses of MTX and the incidence of hematological toxicity [36]. However, just like G80A SNP, there are disputes about the influences of these SNPs, as different studies had different outcomes [37]. Metabolizing enzymes were also being analyzed, given the critical role of transporters in disposition of MTX and its active products, as well as the folate metabolism. MTX pharmacogenetics mostly focused on the SNPs in the MTHFR gene.) e present study shows that genetic polymorphisms in the folate metabolic pathway and in MTX transporters influence the toxicity but not the efficacy of the low-dose MTX treatment in patients with autoimmune diseases [47]. For example, C677T and A1298C are known in MTHFR gene to result in a lower enzyme activity [47]. Windsor and associates reported that MTHFR A1298C and C677T were associated with MTX related nephrotoxicity and anemia [48]. These SNPs might be associated with decreased activity of methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase, elevated plasma homocysteine levels, and altered distribution of folate [49]. Thus patients with this genotype were more vulnerable to potential MTX induced toxicity since these reactions above may lead to slower folate metabolism and slower cell repair [50]. Weisman et al. used univariate logistic regression

to reveal that the MTHFR C677T also increases the occurrence of side effects in central nervous system, manifested as headache and lethargy [51]. However, Lambrecht et al. argued that MTHFR C667T was not a predictive factor for toxicity [50]. Berkani et al. found no association between A1298C polymorphism and MTX toxicity [52]. Interestingly, Grabar et al. claimed that the patients with MTHFR 1298C genotype have a lower risk for MTX toxicity than the carriers of MTHFR 1298A allele [47]. To date, the study of pharmacogenetics of MTX continues. An increasing number of SNPs have been found to be possibly associated with the efficacy and toxicity of MTX. Newly discovered genotypes include C347G in ATIC and 5'-UTR 28-bp repeat and 3'-UTR 6-bp deletion in TYMS, which may influence both efficacy and toxicity of MTX; similarly, factors that may affect MTX associated toxicity are, for example, A2756G in MS and A66G in MTRR [37, 48, 53, 54]. Growing evidences suggest that a single genetic factor is unlikely to adequately predict the efficacy and toxicity of MTX in polygenic disease, such as RA and autoimmune associated ocular disease.

4. Comparison of methotrexate with other DMARDs: By definition, DMARDs in RA are those compounds for which an inhibiting effect on radiographic progression has been demonstrated. Comparisons of MTX with other DMARDs suggested that MTX is probably more efficacious. However, there are some methodological problems with comparisons, one of which is that in most of the early trials rather low dosages of MTX were used. In a multicenter, double-blind trial, 999 patients were randomized to leflunomide (LEF) or oral MTX for 52 weeks [55]. Treatment with MTX resulted in better results for tender and swollen joint counts, physician and patient global assessments, and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR). In a comparative study with oral gold and low dose oral MTX, both medications showed significant improvement in all clinical parameters [56]. However, the beneficial effects appeared earlier and the rates of improvement were stronger with MTX (e.g. improvement in terms of tender and swollen joints in 70% with MTX and in 41% with oral gold), while discontinuations due to adverse effects occurred in 22% of patients on therapy with gold and in 7% on MTX. For comparison, discontinuations due to lack of efficacy were observed in 2.9% in the MTX and in 9.1% in the oral gold group, respectively. The results of the trials comparing parenteral gold to oral MTX revealed similar results. In a Canadian double-blind randomized trial, 18 patients with active RA were treated with 12.5 mg oral MTX and 17 patients with 50 mg parenteral gold for 6 months. The patients improved significantly but there was no major advantage for MTX [57]. In another Canadian trial 20 patients were treated with 10mg oral MTX and 50 mg aurothiomalate, respectively [58]. In a German trial, 87 patients were treated either with intramuscular MTX or aurothiomalate[59]. Discontinuations due to adverse effects were significantly higher in the gold group as well as the severity of adverse effects (74.7% vs 48.3%). Clinical parameters improved in both groups with no significant difference between the compounds. The efficacy of oral MTX and azathioprine (AZA) was compared in a 48-week randomized double-blind trial [60]. The discontinuation rate because of adverse effects and lack of efficacy was significantly higher in the AZA group. After 48 weeks only 36% of patients on AZA but 91% on MTX were still receiving the medication. The improvement of tender joint count and ESR after 24 and 48 weeks was significantly better in the MTX group.

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In a systematic comparison, the traditional DMARDs have recently been compared regarding efficacy and safety [61]. MTX was the most commonly administered drug in patients with RA (29.5%), followed by chloroquine (21.6%). Reasons for discontinuation of DMARD therapy were (i) insufficient efficacy (37%), (ii) subjective side effects (29%), (iii) abnormalities of laboratory parameters (8%) followed by (iv) objective side effects. MTX had the highest retention rate of all tested conventional DMARDs (median drug survival time 40 months) while the lowest retention rate was found for cyclosporine (median drug survival time 13 months). Combinations of several DMARDs did not differ significantly from MTX. In the combined analyses of efficacy and toxicity, MTX and sulfasalazine (SSZ) performed best, chloroquine was not much different.

5. LD-MTX AND HD-MTX Are two different drugs for all practical purposes: It is noteworthy that the mechanism of action, bioavailability and pharmacokinetics, of LD- and HD-MTX are strikingly different. There are four landmark papers clearly establishing the differences between LD-MTX and HD-MTX.^{20–23} Therefore, these two forms of MTX behave like two different drugs for all practical purposes. ^{20–24} LD-MTX used in the treatment of systemic autoimmune rheumatic diseases is administered as weekly mini-pulses at doses of ≤ 25 –30 mg. In contrast, the usual dose in the treatment of cancers is in cycles of 1000 mg or 5000 mg/week; doses up to 13 g of MTX have also been used. Thus, the dosages of MTX used 846 International Journal of Rheumatic Diseases, for the treatment of malignancies are several log-orders higher (i.e., in grams) than the dose prescribed for treating RA and other systemic rheumatic diseases (i.e., in milligrams). It is somewhat similar to aspirin, which is also used as high- and low-doses for different purposes with a different mechanism of action. High-dose aspirin is used for its anti-inflammatory, antipyretic and analgesic properties (doses varying from 1 to 6 gm/day) as against low-dose aspirin with its anti-platelet property commonly used at doses of 75 or 150 mg/day for preventing arterial clotting[62].

6. Combination therapies with biologics: The combination of MTX with biologics has always been superior when compared with either of those medications alone. The majority of the trials have concentrated on patients with an insufficient response to MTX. In many studies this has just been defined subjectively, and this may explain some variance in trial results. However, there are also some studies in MTX negative- patients: a rather different patient population. In a pioneer study in juvenile idiopathic (poly) arthritis (JIA) the efficacy of combining MTX with the 75 kD tumor necrosis factor (TNF) receptor fusion protein etanercept (ETN) was higher than MTX þ placebo in patients who had been resistant to MTX. After 24 weeks ACR 20 and ACR 50 responses were achieved by 71% and 39% of these patients while only 27% and 3% of the placebo group reached those levels, respectively. These response rates were sustained for a 2-year period (median), and many patients could either reduce or completely discontinue the concomitant corticosteroid medication. The combination of infliximab (INF) with MTX also demonstrated good efficacy and safety in adult patients with severe RA: about 60% of the patients achieved a major improvement [63]. Clinical and radiological success of the combination of MTX and infliximab could be shown for a treatment

period of 2 years. Moreover, the combination of MTX with TNF blockers generated a better tolerance towards the antibodies which reportedly occur with INF and adalimumab (ADA) therapy [64]. Similar data have been published for the other TNF blockers ADA [65], golimumab [66] and certolizumab [67], the IL6 receptor antagonist tocilizumab [68], the B-cell depleting agent rituximab and the T-cell stimulation inhibitor abatacept. Taken together, regarding clinical efficacy MTX monotherapy performs almost similarly well in comparison to biologic monotherapy, both usually combined with glucocorticoids [69]. The combination of MTX with biologics is always superior to either monotherapy. Biologics have better efficacy regarding radiographic damage.

7. Radiographic progression: In addition to clinical improvements in disease activity and function, radiographic damage and progression is a very important criterion to judge on the efficacy of DMARDs. There are only a limited number of trials that fulfil essential methodological requirements. Several smaller open and retrospective studies with MTX suggest a positive effect of the drug and seem to slow down the destructive course of the disease [70]. In a German study with 174 patients with early erosive RA a significant retardation of radiographic progression was found in both groups after 1 year of therapy [71]. In a 5-year trial with 60 patients there was significantly less radiographic progression in the patients treated with MTX as compared with penicillamine. Half of the MTX-treated patients showed no radiographic progression some of which were in clinical remission [72]. The radiographic progression of RA patients treated with either AZA or MTX showed that after 6 and 12 months, fewer patients in the latter group had developed new erosions [73]. The radiographic course of RA was studied in patients before and after low-dose MTX pulse therapy. While clinical parameters (morning stiffness, pain and ESR) improved significantly, no significant differences in the development of erosions before and after that treatment were observed. In another study the authors calculated that MTX treatment decelerated the radiographic course of patients with RA by a factor 3 [74]. Taken together, there is no reasonable doubt that MTX does decelerate the radiographic progression in patients with RA [69;Rau, 2010]. However, MTX does not stop radiographic damage in severe RA. As already pointed out, all biologic agents have been shown to increase the efficacy of MTX with regard to the inhibition of radiographic damage [69].

8. Bioavailability and routes of administration: MTX as monotherapy or in a combination with other drugs, including glucocorticoids and biologics, is the most common treatment for RA patients in the world today, and MTX is considered the anchor drug for the vast majority of therapeutic strategies [75]. Although the oral route of administration of MTX is still the most frequently used, there is an increasing tendency to choose the subcutaneous route of administration. The rationale for that is that the bioavailability of oral MTX is rather variable (80%) and several trials have demonstrated that the bioavailability of subcutaneous MTX is superior. Indeed, some clinical studies have also proposed to use subcutaneous MTX as a reasonable alternative and to switch from the oral to the parenteral route of administration [76]. In general, food intake has no major effect on the bioavailability of low dose MTX in patients

with RA . However, although the peak concentration of MTX is not reduced by the intake of food, the time to reach the highest concentration seems slightly longer. In a retrospective chart review of polyarticular juvenile RA (JRA) and RA patients, an equal efficacy of oral, subcutaneous and intramuscular ways of administration was reported. Furthermore, the parenteral routes were tolerated better and fewer gastrointestinal side effects were observed. However, taken together there is no data that convincingly prove that parenteral MTX is associated with less gastrointestinal tract side effects in comparison to the oral route. Clinical experience tells that this is rather variable which indicates that there are patients who tolerate tablets better than injections and the other way round. The role of absorption limitation of MTX has been studied by Hoekstra and colleagues [77] by comparing the bioavailability of a divided higher (2535 mg weekly) oral dose of MTX in comparison with a single dose in 10 adult patients with RA. The bioavailability of the split dose was 28% higher compared with the single-dose group with a median weekly oral dose of 30 mg MTX. Compared with a historical subcutaneous control group the relative bioavailability was 0.76 and 0.9 for the single dose and the split dose group, respectively. Thus, when higher MTX doses are needed, splitting the oral dose may be an option and a suitable alternative for subcutaneous administration.

9. Dosage and response to methotrexate: Many studies have tried to explain and identify indicators of a good response to MTX therapy. From the pharmacological point of view, MTX is an antifolate prodrug, metabolized by polyglutamate synthetase into MTX polyglutamates (PGs): this leads to the addition of 27 glutamic residues to the parent drug. These MTXPGs are metabolites which are produced in different forms (length). Dependent on the number of residues short- or long-chain MTXPGs arise, and this may have an influence on clinical efficacy and tolerability. Analyzing the accumulation of different MTXPGs in erythrocytes in correlation to the effect of switching from oral to parenteral MTX in 10 RA patients with insufficiently controlled disease activity showed an increase of MTXPGs [78]. The authors hypothesized that this accumulation of long chain MTXPGs may be the reason for an increased efficacy of MTX. Similar results were reported in patients with JIA (n ¼ 99); the subcutaneous route of administration was also associated with higher proportions of intracellular long-chain MTXPG. Since a study on dose escalation of oral MTX in patients with RA also showed a selective distribution toward intracellular long-chain MTXPGs it appears that the selective emergence of these active metabolites may be mainly a function of dose intensity. Somewhat different results came from a recent multicenter study with a total of 256 patients who received low-dose MTX for at least 3 months [79]. A large interpatient variability in MTX dosing (range 525 mg/ week) and MTXPG accumulation was found. The most impressive result was that the increase of MTXPG3 levels was associated with 25-fold higher likelihood of a response to MTX. Furthermore, the addition of glutamic residues appeared to even enhance the efficacy. Taken together, these interesting results should lead to further studies on the subject.

10. Efficacy of subcutaneous methotrexate: Several studies have been performed but only one was powered enough to directly compare the clinical efficacy and tolerability of oral versus subcutaneous MTX: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled, multicenter study

recently performed in Germany with 384 MTX-naïve active early RA patients (DAS284) who were randomly assigned to either oral MTX (15 mg given as two 7.5 mg tablets plus dummy prefilled syringe) or subcutaneous MTX (15 mg as prefilled syringe at 10 mg/ml plus dummy tablets) for 4 months. At week 16, ACR20 non-responders were switched from oral MTX to 15 mg subcutaneous and from 15 mg subcutaneous to 20 mg subcutaneous for the remaining 8 weeks. In addition patients received 5 mg folic acid given 24 h after MTX. The parenteral route of administration was more successful than the oral form in almost all analyses after 4 months. After treatment for 6 months, 34% (subcutaneous) versus 24% (oral) of the patients were in remission, respectively: a relative increase of 42%. More than 50% of the patients reached 'good' improvement (EULAR criteria) when receiving subcutaneous MTX: an increase of 30% compared with tablets. This study clearly showed that, at the same dose level, the subcutaneous application is more efficacious than the oral route [80]. A direct comparison of treatment strategies with an increased oral dosage has not been performed so far. It would be especially interesting to learn whether a higher oral dose of MTX will lead to less side effects while potentially being as efficacious as a lower dose given parenterally [81].

11. Addition of folic acid: Since some MTX toxicities can be interpreted on the basis of folate deficiency, supplementation strategies with various folates have been studied. On the other hand, excessive doses of folic acid can negate MTX efficacy in RA, however more moderate doses of both folic acid and folinic acid have been shown to reduce toxic manifestations [82]. Overall, the question of whether or to what degree folate supplementation may affect MTX efficacy has still not been completely answered. One reason for this is that it is a complicated issue; for example, one interpretation of the data is that folic acid supplementation allows a higher dose of MTX to be tolerated, thereby increasing its efficacy. Furthermore, folic acid supplementation was shown to have a favorable effect on homocystein metabolism and may have other effects on MTX metabolism such as lowering the formation of less active metabolites such as 7-OH-MTX [82]. The optimal dosing regimen for folic acid and folinic acid is as yet unknown and without reasonable doubt a balance between MTX, and folate dose is important. In general, there seems to be a broader margin of safety using folic acid. Furthermore, the lower cost does argue for folic acid. The potential of folic acid interfering with MTX absorption can be overcome by giving it 24 hours prior to the weekly MTX dose or 24 hours following the dose [82].

12. Toxicity in general

12.1 Adverse events: To examine the adverse events in patients receiving MTX, we retained and pooled the results from the 21 prospective studies presenting the number of adverse events (table 1). Thus, among 3463 patients with RA who received on average a low dose of MTX (8.8 mg/week) for a mean duration of 36.5 months, 72.9% of patients had at least one adverse event. The most common adverse events were gastrointestinal and elevation of liver enzymes. Kremer et al performed a long observational study (up to 104 months, mean doses of MTX between 12.4 and 14.6 mg/ week) in a small number of patients (level of evidence 2b). 21–23 At baseline, 29 patients were included and after 79 months, 20 remained in the study. The

prevalence of patients who experienced side effects after 2 years of treatment was 79–85% and constant over time (up to 104 months). Gastrointestinal adverse events were the most common side effect (52–65%) and had similar incidence whatever the duration of MTX. Elevations of liver enzymes (above the upper limit of normal) occurred especially during the first 4 years of treatment (69–88%) and then decreased (25% then 15% after 79 months). The number of neurological events (headache, light headedness, fatigue, vertigo, feeling “out of sorts”, 21–38%) and leukopenia (20–25%) also remained constant over time. Four withdrawals occurred before 53 months of treatment. Using the ARAMIS data bank (Arthritis Rheumatism and Aging Medical Information System), Fries et al compared the toxicity of commonly used DMARDs in RA (level 2b). They used a toxicity index computed from clinical symptoms, laboratory abnormalities and hospitalizations reported by patients, health professionals and doctors. According to this score, HCQ was statistically less toxic than all other DMARDs, while auranofin was the most toxic. HCQ was followed by intramuscular gold and as one group closely together D-penicillamine, MTX and azathioprine. This toxicity score is not usually routinely used probably because of its complexity[83-86].

12.2 Methotrexate pneumonitis: According to the results from the 21 prospective studies, only 15 cases of MTX pneumonitis occurred among the 3463 patients with RA receiving MTX (0.43%) up to 36.5 months (table 1) [87]. MTX pneumonitis, considered as an acute hypersensitivity reaction, occurs early in the course of MTX, thus it does not seem to be a problem of long-term treatment by MTX.

12.3 Cytopenia relative to long-term MTX treatment: Table 1 also shows data on cytopenia: 179 events of cytopenia in one cell line (5.2%) occurred in patients with RA receiving MTX up to 36.5 months. The rate of thrombocytopenia was 4.1% in a retrospective study.28 Pancytopenia seems to be less common with an incidence of 0.96–1.4% in a few retrospective studies.

12.4 Mortality in patients with RA who received long-term MTX: The mortality IR of the MTX group (23 per 1000 person-years) was in line with the IR in the group not receiving MTX (26.7 per 1000 person-years). Moreover, MTX may provide a survival benefit by reducing cardiovascular mortality in comparison with patients with RA treated with other DMARDs (adjusted hazard ratio of cardiovascular mortality 0.3 (95% CI 0.2 to 0.7). However, in the retrospective cohort the RR for mortality was 3.4 in patients with RA with a history of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) starting MTX as compared with patients with RA without CVD who started MTX and patients who started other DMARDs and patients with CVD but not receiving MTX[87].

12.5 Lymphoma and malignancies: Overall, patients with RA have an increased risk of lymphoma in comparison with the general population, which is mainly related to high levels of disease activity. A relationship between MTX treatment and the occurrence of lymphoproliferative disorders (LPDs) in RA has been topic of discussion for many years. The studies included in this review did not allow us to assess fully the risk of long-term MTX

treatment on the occurrence of lymphoma and malignancies in patients with RA, although there does not seem to be an indication of an increased risk. For the risk of lymphoma, most of the studies compared MTX groups with the general population and not with patients with RA who did not receive MTX. Wolfe's study is the only study providing the incidence rates of lymphoma in patients with RA with and without MTX. In the MTX group, this rate is higher than in the "no MTX, no biological agent" group. Unfortunately, no adjustment on RA severity was performed. Thus this higher incidence might be due to a higher severity of RA in the MTX group and not to the drug effect itself. For other malignancies, there are no data on the risk of MTX use in comparison with patients with RA who have received other DMARDs as a control group[88].

12.6 Liver toxicity in patients with RA who received long-term MTX: Elevation of liver enzymes is the second most common adverse event during MTX treatment after gastrointestinal side effects. To evaluate the incidence of elevation of liver enzymes, we pooled the results from 27 prospective studies that evaluated a total of 3808 patients with RA who received a low dose of MTX (10.5 mg/week) during 55.8 months, on average. 4–24 32–37 A total of 769 patients had at least one episode of elevated liver enzymes (20.2%), 12.9% had an elevation up to two times the upper limit of normal and 3.7% of patients stopped MTX because of liver toxicity[89].

12.7 Liver damage evaluated on liver biopsy: One meta-analysis provides the results of sequential liver biopsies performed systematically in patients receiving MTX. These results have to be judged with caution because these studies were all uncontrolled and some do not report baseline biopsy results. The meta-analysis suggests that 3% of patients would develop severe fibrosis or cirrhosis over 55 months' treatment with MTX, especially if they drink at least 100 g of alcohol a week (corresponding to 10 glasses a week). In the two studies with baseline biopsies, not a single patient had evidence of severe fibrosis or cirrhosis after 4 years of treatment (cumulative dose of MTX around 2000 mg[90]

13. Summary

MTX is still very much at the center of all therapeutic strategies for RA and other rheumatic diseases. MTX is frequently combined with NSAIDs and corticosteroids, other conventional DMARDs and biologics. The latter clearly enhance the efficacy of MTX, especially regarding the inhibition of radiographic progression. The parenteral way of administration of MTX is superior to the oral route, presumably because of the better bioavailability. There is also data to support a role of intracellular MTX polyglutamates in that regard. Whether increasing the oral dosage leads to similar clinical effects with-out increasing the toxicity remains to be shown.

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